

TEMPORAL ORGANIZATION OF THE TEXT OF NEWSPAPER PUBLICISM

Kobalia L.

Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor, Sokhumi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11199375>

Abstract

A text of newspaper publicism within mass communication is considered in relation to social contexts of language use. This paper is primarily concerned with the modern linguistic theory of the text covering very wide range of problems. The research of a text as independent subject of the linguistic analysis is carried out at the different levels, in various directions and aspects both in the theoretical and practical plan. Data on temporal structure of the text, is still currently rather fragmentary, being collected in linguistics, on the one hand, in connection with the latest researches in the field of the category of tense, on the other hand, in connection with studying of genre and functional and semantic features of temporal structure of different types of the text, at last, in connection with a problem of functional and semantic types of speech, and with consideration of the use of time as one of structural grammatical features of this or that functional and semantic type of speech.

Keywords: temporal organization of the text; structural-semantic features of the text; functional-semantic types of speech.

The modern linguistic theory of the text covers very wide range of problems, and a text research as independent subject of the linguistic analysis is carried out at different levels, in various directions and aspects both in the theoretical and practical plan. Data on temporal structure of the text is still currently rather fragmentary being collected in linguistics, on the one hand in connection with the latest researches in the field of the category of tense, on the other hand in connection with studying of genre and functional and semantic features of temporal structure of different types of the text, and at last, in connection with a problem of functional and semantic types of speech, and with consideration of usage of time as one of structural grammatical features of this or that functional and semantic type of speech. In the given paper under the temporality is understood a text category in which by means of morphological, lexical, lexical-syntactic means and extra-linguistic factors is expressed the author's subjective and estimative attitude to the objective tense reflected in the text forming a grammatical text type in plan of its temporal structure. Temporary forms of a verb at the level of the publicistic text are multifunctional and multiple-valued, that is the same temporary form being capable to act at the level of the publicistic text in several qualities serving semantic and syntagmatic orderliness of the text.

The research task is to substantiate the analysis technique of text temporal organization of the newspaper reportage "Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung" - to show structural-semantic features of text, norm of tense usage in this genre of newspaper journalism and analyze comprehensively text-forming functions of tense category. The researched problem is actual from the position of text grammar as the newspaper doesn't represent a single text, but a set system of texts united by unity of time and the place of formation a single ideological content, and having own structural model. The research of structural and substantial organization of text among other problems has proposed on the agenda also a problem of the temporal organization of the text. In general form the position on text-forming function

of category of tense has been already expressed in first works on linguistics of text and a sign of temporal integrity has been attributed both to the text in the narrow sense of the word – to super-phrase unity, and to the text – as the whole speech formation.

It should be noted that Harald Weinrich's works have special value concerning to a particular importance for studying of temporal structure of the text in general, and also features of temporary registration of separate functional and semantic types of speech in modern German. In his book "Tempus. Besprochene und erzählte Welt" H. Weinrich separates the use of tenses in German into two subsystems and connects them to his concept of the "world of reasoning" and "the world of narrative". According to H. Weinrich, the subject of linguistics is two categories of tense: paradigmatic - tense in a temporal system and syntagmatic - contextual tense together with other neighboring tenses. Tense in live speech, in sentence, and in text can occur in infinite combinations with other tenses, but one tense is given clear priority, especially in complex sentences and in those cases where the tense of the main clause determines the tense of the subordinate clause, and which has received the name of **consecutio temporum**. As tense forms of the "reasoning world" H. Heinrich considers Präsens, Perfekt, Futurum I and Futurum II (the so-called group I of tense forms) to be the tense forms of the "narrative world" respectively Präteritum, Plusquamperfekt, Konditionalis I and Konditionalis II (II group of tenses).

In the expressions **er singt** and **er sang** the data about the tense of singing process are absent. Präsens and Präteritum in these sentences give us the chance to understand whether singing process is discussed or narrated about it. The discussed singing demands usually instant expression of the viewpoint. But if the process of singing is narrated about, then information on it isn't urgent [2, S. 36-45]. More or less similar judgments of separate tenses have been stated also by some other researchers. As for Perfekt, Kaj B. Lindgren writes that this tense is subjective judgment, expression of thought. It is used in dialogue and is followed by the

adverbs: **schon** and **noch**. Kaj B. Lindgren notices in Perfekt shade of reference to speaking "I" [1, S. 97]. H. Weinrich adds to it that the function of Perfekt and is found in comparison with Präteritum. On the ground of Präteritum Perfekt appears in the text in strictly certain cases. The same text can be submitted at the same time both in the form of the narration and in the form of reasoning, and verbal forms of both temporary groups can be respectively used. The text reporting this or that fact can begin with Perfekt and continue in Präteritum. It means that Perfekt not only emphasizes an event of retrospectivity, but also gives a reasoning shade to this event. The given circumstance is an essential sign of this tense [2, S. 36-45].

H. Weinrich's thought on various temporal registrations of various types of the text and on dependence of the choice of a temporary form on a speech situation and our attempts to connect the use of these or those tense forms with a common problem of structural language signs of the main functional and semantic types of speech allocated by us – reasonings, narrations and descriptions in the text of the reportage of the newspaper "Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung" are close. The reportage is fairly considered in the theory of journalism as one of the most effective genres the functioning of which in the newspaper represents striking peculiar feature of a newspaper publicistic style. Distinctive feature of the reporting is the direct inclusiveness of the author in the described event - or as an observer, or as an active participant. The reporter is faced by a task to present this event as being happened in the face of the reader, to create by use of graphic and expression means its exact and figurative picture. Important means of achievement of this purpose is the effect of the author's presence on the place of an event. The originality of the reportage of the newspaper "Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung" is shown in its composition. As a rule, the facts are interpreted in the sequence in which they took place actually. It is clear: the requirement of documentary accuracy of the reporting belongs both to the right time when there were described events, and to sequence of illustration of the facts. Let's consider correlation in speech the reportage of the most characteristic to its composite elements – reasoning, narrations and descriptions. The description in the reportage is concluded in the image of a number of signs, phenomena, objects or events which are necessary to imagine everything at the same time. The narration, contrary to the description, is the image of the events or the phenomena which are not made not simultaneously, but following one after another or determining each other. The reasoning in the reporting aims to find out any thought and construct the logical scheme of conclusions. The narration in the reportage of the newspaper "Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung" generally happens in the form of Präteritum. Sometimes Präteritum is combined with Plusquamperfekt. The narration is often replaced by the description. The description is not given objectively but through the author's perception directly and openly revealing the narrator's "I". Subjective and emotional character of the description brings closer the reader to

a situation of events, makes the description as a reporting element. Here "I" is neither a kind of stylization, nor artistic method, but it is the author's original "I". The description is made by Präsens and contacting to it Perfekt, as this speech type serves evident, consecutive display of the course of events and at the same time the reporter defines the position to what he writes about, drawing the corresponding conclusions.

All facts stated in reportings of this newspaper are proved and disproved by means of a reasoning which has to be presented in very convincing form. The basis of the reporting is made by the most important, the characteristic, carefully selected facts of which there is an event, and author's arguments, reasonings give to these facts emotional coloring, approve their reliability, and at the same time reproduce the whole figurative picture of an event. The reasoning takes place in the form of generalizing, sometimes punctual Präsens as this type of speech is sometimes presented also in a moment of statement. Being characteristic to the newspaper "Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung" reporting, sometimes sharp change of functional and semantic types of the speech – description, narration and reasoning creates dynamism of expression, a polyphonic picture of reality. If to use H. Weinrich's known concept on "the world under reasoning" and "the world under narration" [2, S. 36-45] as the publicistic genre of the newspaper "Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung", it can be stated that in this genre "the world under reasoning" prevails being characteristic to it verbal forms. However, it seems to us that the text of the reportage has two temporal dominants each forming one of its composite parts: the narrating part is formed by Präteritum (more often, in a combination with Plusquamperfekt), the description and reasoning is formed by means of Präsens (sometimes contacting to it Perfekt).

The data obtained as a result of researching temporal structure of the text in the reportage of the newspaper "Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung" are of interest from the viewpoint of revealing interconditionality between functional and semantic types of speech or system of the functional and semantic types of speech defining composition of this publicistic genre and temporal model of corresponding texts. As language of newspaper is not a unique genre of newspaper prose, it is acceptable to raise a question not only of temporal structure of the text - a representative of each newspaper genre, but also about temporal structure in general as sets of these genres. Of course, it is impossible to claim categorically that there is a rigid, unambiguous communication between certain functional and semantic types of speech, on the one hand, and the use of this or that temporary form, with another. However relative definiteness of temporal registration of various functional and semantic types of speech in relation to this genre of the text is undoubted.

References:

1. Lindgren Kaj B. Über den oberdeutschen Präteritumschwund. - Helsinki, 1957, - S. 97.
2. Weinrich H. Tempus. Besprochene und erzählte Welt. - München: Beck, 2001, - S. 36-45.